

Chemical Examination of the Seeds of *Caesalpinia* *Bonducella*, Flem. Part I.

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The so-called bonduc seeds or "fever nuts" are obtained from *Cassalpinia Bonducella*, Flem (*Guilandia Bonducella*, Linn.), a climbing prickly shrub cosmopolitan in the tropics and common all over Bengal, Bombay and practically the whole of Southern India. These seeds have been known to Ayurvedic pharmacists for a long time as anti-periodic and the Indigenous Drugs Committee have recommended them very favourably as a powerful tonic and a valuable febrifuge.

The authors of "Pharmacographia" (Fluckiger and Hansbury, 2nd edition, p. 212) isolated a non-alkaloidal bitter principle from the kernels. Heckel and Schlagdenhauffen (*Compt. rend.*, 1886, 103, 89) obtained from the cotyledons a non-alkaloidal bitter principle as a white amorphous powder to which they assigned the name "bonducin" and the formula $C_{14}H_{15}O_5$ and attributed to it the physiological properties of the seeds. Bacon (*Philippine J. Sci.*, 1906, 1, Part II, 1032) was able to isolate from the kernels the bitter principle "bonducin" which he found to be not a glucoside but a mixture of complex resinous bodies. He could not obtain any alkaloid or glucoside from the alcoholic extract of the kernels. Bhaduri (*Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 26, 59) under the title "The glucoside and the oil of *Caesalpinia Bonducella*" states that the seeds yield an alkaloid for which the author suggests the name 'natin.' No details of this brief report are published; hence it is doubtful whether 'natin' is a glucoside or an alkaloid. Godbole, Paranjpe, and Shrikhande (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6,

295) found that the bitter principle of the kernels extracted with alcohol contained all the sulphur of bonducella nut and reduced Fehling's solution after hydrolysis. They concluded, therefore, that the bitter principle is a glucoside.

From the preceding brief review of the literature, it will be observed that the statements respecting the physiologically active constituents of the seeds are very divergent and to a large extent, inconclusive. In view of the medicinal use of the bonduc seeds and the deficiency of our knowledge respecting their other constituents, it seemed desirable to subject them to a complete chemical examination. It was also thought possible that thereby, in conjunction with pharmacological tests, some further and more definite information might be obtained as to the character of the constituent upon which their reputed action as a febrifuge depends.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The material employed for this investigation consisted of a quantity of white kernels (about 40 per cent. of the whole seeds) obtained by breaking fully matured and dry seeds from the local market.

Preliminary Examination.

Test for alkaloids. 15 G. of the ground material were digested with Prollius' solution for two hours and the mixture filtered. The filtrate, on being examined in the usual manner for the presence of alkaloids, gave negative results.

Test for enzymes. 100 G. of the ground material were shaken for 18 hours with cold water. The mixture which was observed to have developed a considerable amount of gas (probably carbon dioxide) was allowed to settle. The top aqueous layer was filtered through paper with great difficulty. The filtrate was found to contain a large amount of a reducing sugar and soluble organic acids. (The original powder contained only a trace of a reducing sugar and no soluble organic acids). The presence of these compounds and the gas would indicate the existence of one or more enzymes which have probably acted upon the carbohydrate material to produce them.

Steam distillation. 300 G. of the material were distilled with steam and about 600-700 c.c. of the distillate were collected. The latter, which was not acidic, was then extracted thoroughly with redistilled ether, the ethereal liquid dried and the solvent removed. A very small amount of a pale yellow oily material (0.003 g.) was thus obtained.

Test for starch, other carbohydrates, tannin, &c. 10 G_m of the material were thoroughly mixed with 100 c.c. of distilled water and warmed on the water-bath for about half an hour. The mixture was then allowed to settle, decanted and filtered. The filtrate when tested for—

- (1) starch with dilute iodine solution indicated its presence,
- (2) tannin with ferric chloride indicated its absence,
- (3) reducing sugar with Fehling's solution showed the presence of only a trace of some reducing sugar, and for

(4) polysaccharides (after hydrolysis with dilute hydrochloric acid) with Fehling's solution developed a heavy precipitate of cuprous oxide suggesting the presence of a considerable amount of a polysaccharide. This heavy reduction might be due to glucose formed by the hydrolysis of starch, the presence of which has already been demonstrated; but the sweet taste of the original liquid would indicate that a disaccharide is at least partially responsible for the reduction after hydrolysis.

Extraction with different solvents. In order to ascertain the general character of the constituents, 25 g. of the ground material were extracted with various solvents successively in a Soxhlet apparatus when the following amounts of extract, dried at 100°, were obtained:

Petroleum ether (low-boiling)	extracted	4.92 g.	= 19.7 per cent.
Ethyl ether	..	0.18 g.	= 0.7
Chloroform	..	0.44 g.	= 1.8 ..
Ethyl acetate	..	0.15 g.	= 0.6 ..
Ethyl alcohol (95 per cent.)	..	2.16 g.	= 8.6 ..
Total		<u>7.85 g.</u>	= 31.4 per cent.

Fig. 1.

kernels) which has been examined separately.

For the purpose of a complete examination, 15 kg. of the finely powdered material (corresponding with 37.5 kg. of the seeds) were extracted completely by percolating with cold 90 per cent. alcohol. After removal of the greater part of the solvent by distillation under reduced pressure, there remained a reddish-brown extract. This was mixed with the dry residue from another lot of 2 kg. of the powdered nut obtained after thorough extraction first with alcohol and then with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-70°) and from alcohol over the water-bath. The dry material was then extracted in a modified continuous extraction apparatus (Fig. 1) described by Sando *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1924, 16, 1125), successively with low-boiling petroleum ether, ethyl ether, chloroform, ethyl acetate and lastly with ethyl alcohol and the various extracts thus obtained were examined separately.

The residual powder after percolation with cold alcohol was extracted with low-boiling petroleum ether. This extract after the removal of the solvent gave a clear pale yellow, non-bitter oil (about 9 per cent. of the

I. Petroleum Ether Extract.

This was a viscous brown material and had a bitter taste indicating the presence of the bitter principle. In order to remove this as far as possible, the whole of the extract was shaken several times with cold 90 per cent. alcohol. The combined alcohol solution was filtered.

1. Alcohol-soluble Portion.

The solvent was distilled off and the residue dissolved in a very small volume of chloroform. This chloroform solution was then poured into a flask containing a large volume of low-boiling petroleum

ether. The mixture immediately turned milky and on standing in an ice-box for 5—6 days, deposited a pale yellow solid.

Isolation of the Bitter Principle (A).

The yellow solid was an amorphous powder with a very bitter taste. A larger amount of this material was subsequently obtained from the ethyl ether extract (II) and its composition and characteristics will be recorded in connection with the latter.

The mixture of the solvents from the filtrate was distilled and the brown viscous oily residue (about 125 g.) was saponified with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution. The alcohol was then distilled and the residual strongly alkaline soap mixed with purified filter-paper pulp, dried and extracted with ethyl ether in a Soxhlet apparatus.

Examination of Unsaponifiable Matter.

The ethereal extract was washed with water and the solvent removed by distillation. As the extract was being concentrated, a white solid material began to separate out. After concentrating to a small volume and cooling, the substance was filtered and washed with ether. The filtrate on standing deposited a little more of this material which was recovered in a similar manner.

Isolation of a Phytosterolin (B) (Phytosterol glucoside).

The above mentioned white substance, m. p. 228-229°, was crystallised from ethyl alcohol in white microscopic rectangular crystals melting at 284-285°. The filtrate on concentration and cooling gave another crop of crystals melting at 232-234°. The latter is apparently an impure specimen of the same compound.

This compound gave the usual colour reactions of phytosterols. When hydrolysed with amyl alcoholic hydrochloric acid solution in the manner described by Power and Salway (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 404) in connection with the hydrolysis of ipuranol, it yielded a phytosterol (C) which crystallised from ethyl alcohol in glistening leaflets, m. p. 122-123°, and gave an acetate, m. p. 109-111°. The sugar (apparently glucose) produced by the hydrolysis was found to reduce Fehling's solution very readily but the amount was not sufficient for the preparation of the osazone.

It is therefore evident that the compound is a phytosterolin. It is interesting to note that the phytosterol (C) obtained by the hydrolysis of this compound has been isolated also in a free condition during the course of this investigation.

Isolation of a Phytosterol (D).

The ethereal filtrate after the removal of phytosterolin was distilled and the dark brown viscous residue dissolved in hot alcohol and treated with 1 per cent. hot alcoholic solution of digitonin. The phytosterol which was recovered from the precipitate in the usual manner melted at 132-133° after three crystallisations from alcohol. This compound gave the common colour reactions of phytosterols as well as an acetate melting at 119-120°. These properties indicate its identity with sitosterol.

The solvent from the alcoholic filtrate after the removal of the digitonin-phytosterol precipitate was removed by distillation and the residue freed from the excess of digitonin. The brown viscous oil (15-16 g.) thus obtained was distilled at 140-160°/ 3-4 mm. when only 3-4 g. of a light yellow oil (E) came over. All attempts to distill at higher temperatures resulted in the decomposition of the residue. The yellow oil was found to have an iodine value (Hanus) of 95.4. From the dark coloured distillation residue nothing definite could be isolated.

Examination of Fatty Acids.

These were examined in general, in the same manner as described in detail in Part II, in connection with the examination of the fatty oil. The mixture of acids was found to contain palmitic, stearic, probably lignoceric and small amounts of unsaturated acids of molecular weight lower than that of oleic acid.

2. *Alcohol-insoluble Portion.*

The dark coloured viscous oil left after the extraction with cold alcohol was saponified with alcoholic sodium hydroxide solution, the solvent distilled, and the residual soap dried on filter-paper pulp as described before. The dry soap was then extracted with ethyl ether in a continuous extraction apparatus. During the course of extraction some white solid material separated out from the extract.

Examination of Unsaponifiable Matter.

The ether extract was concentrated to about 200 c.c. and allowed to stay in the ice-box for some hours. The white solid material that had separated out was removed by filtration.

Isolation of a Phytosterolin (F).—Ipuranol, C₃₃H₅₈O₆.

The white solid when crystallised twice from ethyl alcohol gave a compound melting at 289-290°. This gave the usual colour reactions of phytosterols and an acetate melting at 162-163°. These results indicated its identity with ipuranol. This view was further confirmed by determining the mixed melting points of the compound and its acetyl derivative with those of ipuranol and its acetyl derivative respectively isolated from *Coscinium Fensstratum*, Cole.

Isolation of a Phytosterol (C).

The solvent from the ethereal filtrate after the removal of ipuranol was removed by distillation and the viscous oily residue which immediately solidified, was crystallised twice from ethyl alcohol. The product obtained was a snow-white crystalline substance, m.p. 122-124°. The combined filtrates on concentration gave some more of this compound. This product which yielded an acetyl derivative melting at 109-111° was identified as a phytosterol by its colour reactions. The filtrate was carefully examined; but only a small amount of an orange-coloured oily material could be isolated from it.

Examination of Fatty Acids.

These were also examined in the same manner as described in detail in Part II. The mixture was found to contain oleic, linoleic and small amounts of unsaturated acids of lower molecular weight, together with a saturated acid of melting point 54·5°-55·5° and molecular weight 271-272. The latter was probably a mixture of palmitic and stearic acids.

II. Ethyl Ether Extract.

After the removal of the solvent, the extract left a dark red viscous matter which had a very bitter taste. Attempts to obtain any crystalline material from this were unsuccessful. The whole material was then dissolved in a small volume of chloroform and the

solution poured into a flask containing a large excess of low-boiling petroleum ether. The pale yellow flocculent precipitate which immediately separated out was filtered, washed with petroleum ether and dried. The mixture of solvents from the filtrate was distilled and from the small amount of the oily residue nothing definite could be isolated.

Examination of the Bitter Principle (A).

The pale yellow material when reprecipitated as described above was obtained as an amorphous almost white powder. This was mixed with the similar bitter principle obtained from the petroleum ether extract (I) and examined further.

Elementary analysis proved the absence of nitrogen, sulphur and halogens. It left no ash on ignition indicating the presence of carbon, hydrogen and probably oxygen.

It is easily soluble in alcohol, glacial acetic acid, benzene and chloroform, less soluble in ethyl ether, sparingly soluble in petroleum ether and practically insoluble in water. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with the formation of a dark brown colour. Its solution in concentrated nitric acid is yellow and in concentrated hydrochloric acid it has a pink tinge.

The melting point of the material was very indefinite. One fraction softened at 117° and completely melted at 126°. This when reprecipitated as described before gave a very pale yellow product which softened at 138° and melted at 144°. This product on a further similar treatment gave a substance which softened at 128° and melted at 133°. Thus all attempts to get a fraction of constant melting point were unsuccessful. This clearly indicated that the bitter principle was not a homogeneous compound but a complex mixture of resinous bodies.

0.5 G. of the material in neutral alcohol required 10.4 c.c. of *N/20* sodium hydroxide solution for neutralization (phenolphthalein). The substance also dissolves in aqueous sodium hydroxide solution on warming. These reactions indicate that the bitter principle is probably an acid-resin. A chloroform solution (2 per cent.) did not show any optical activity.

The bitter powder was heated on the water-bath with 5 per cent. hydrochloric acid solution for about an hour. The mixture was filtered, the filtrate neutralised with sodium carbonate solution and treated with Fehling's solution. The mixture on being heated on

the water-bath for about 20 minutes did not develop any cuprous oxide, thus indicating the absence of any reducing sugar.

All these reactions confirm the view of Bacon (*loc. cit.*) that the bitter principle is a complex non-alkaloidal and non-glucosidic mixture of resins. The conclusion of Godbole, Paranjpe, and Shrikhande (*loc. cit.*) that the bitter principle is a glucoside containing sulphur could not therefore be verified. The reduction test they obtained after the hydrolysis of the alcoholic bitter extract is apparently due to sucrose which has been isolated from the alcoholic extract (V) and completely identified.

III. Chloroform Extract.

The solvent from the extract was removed and the dark red viscous residue after standing for some time had solidified. Attempts to redissolve this material in chloroform however, proved unsuccessful. Only a very small portion appeared to go in solution. The remaining material was practically insoluble in ether, acetone and alcohol; when warmed on the water-bath with chloroform the whole of the material swelled up and formed a dark red jelly. The latter when heated, lost the solvent and left a resinous product of the consistency of rubber (G). This material was not bitter but had a peculiar taste of its own. On account of its peculiar physical properties no further work could be done. From the material that was dissolved in chloroform a small amount of the bitter principle (A) was obtained.

IV. Ethyl Acetate Extract.

The extract after the removal of the solvent left a very small amount of a waxy residue too small for further work.

V. Alcohol Extract.

The residue after the removal of the solvent when dissolved in water left only a very small amount of a resinous body. The aqueous solution was treated with basic lead acetate and the yellow slimy precipitate was filtered and washed thoroughly with water.

Identification of a Saponin Material (H).

The precipitate was suspended in water, decomposed with hydrogen sulphide and the liquid filtered. The filtrate when concentrated

under reduced pressure yielded a yellow liquid which frothed considerably on shaking and yielded, on hydrolysis, a reducing sugar very readily. These properties would indicate the presence of a saponin material in the liquid.

Isolation of Sucrose (I).

After removing the excess of lead from the filtrate from the lead acetate precipitate, it was concentrated and the syrupy material that was left was digested with hot 95 per cent. alcohol. The alcohol solution was filtered and allowed to stand in the ice-box for about a week. The rhombic crystalline material that had separated out was removed and was found to soften at 161° and decompose at 168°. Its sweet aqueous solution was dextro-rotatory and reduced Fehling's solution only after hydrolysis. These properties indicated that the compound was sucrose. This view was further confirmed by the fact that its aqueous solution after being treated with the invertase preparation from yeast was laevo-rotatory and readily yielded an osazone melting at 204-205°.

Identification of Glucose (J).

The filtrate after the removal of sucrose was concentrated and the last traces of alcohol removed. The aqueous solution of the residue which reduced Fehling's solution to some extent yielded a small amount of an osazone melting at 205°. This indicated the presence of a small amount of free glucose in the aqueous solution.

Therapeutic Value of "Bonducin."

From the chemical nature of the constituents so far isolated only the bitter principle, "bonducin" seemed to have any physiological action. In order to have some idea of its activity it was administered in doses of 0.2 g. along with honey to malarious patients in one of the Ayurvedic hospitals of Poona. Six out of eight cases were reported as successful.

In connection with the isolation of the aforesaid phytosterolins and phytosterols it is interesting to note that the former as well as the latter which are obtained from the former on hydrolysis are found in the plant kingdom very frequently together. Thus the phytosterolin which yields sitosterol on hydrolysis and which was designated as ipuranol before its glucosidic nature was discovered

is commonly found in plant materials as sitosterol itself. Wherever ipuranol has been reported to occur the presence of sitosterol has also been reported; and in some cases where phytosterolins different from ipuranol are reported, phytosterols different from sitosterol are also found (*cf.* Power and Moore, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 99; *ibid.*, 1909, 95, 1985; Rogerson, *ibid.*, 1910, 97, 1004; Power and Salway, *ibid.*, 1913, 103, 191.) Probably these phytosterolins would have yielded the corresponding phytosterols on hydrolysis. Such is the case with the phytosterolin melting at 234°-235°. Though a large number of phytosterols have been reported so far, the number of phytosterolins found so far are very small. This is due to the fact that the latter occur in plant materials in very small amounts and their isolation and subsequent identification therefore, is very difficult unless a large amount of the crude material is handled.

Looking over the various constituents isolated and their properties it seems evident that 'bonducin' is the active principle of the seeds; but a correct conclusion respecting its activity could apparently only be formed when it is tested more systematically with reference to its particular value as a febrifuge.

Summary.

Preliminary examination of the kernels of *C. Bonducella* showed the presence of enzymes, starch, a small amount of a reducing sugar, considerable amount of a disaccharide and the absence of any tannin or alkaloidal material.

The alcoholic extract of the kernels on being separated into various fractions depending upon its partial solubility in the common organic solvents and further examined, has been found to contain the following compounds:

Petroleum ether extract: 'Bonducin,' the bitter resinous acid which could be isolated only in the form of an amorphous white powder of indefinite melting point; palmitic, stearic, probably lignoceric, oleic, linoleic acids and a mixture of unsaturated acids of lower molecular weight; two phytosterolins, one melting at 234°-235° and the other melting at 289°-290° (acetate, m.p. 162°-163°) and hence identical with ipuranol; two phytosterols, one melting at 122°-123° (acetate, m.p. 109°-111°) and the other melting at 182°-183° (acetate,

m.p. 119°-120°) and hence identified as sitosterol; and an unsaponifiable unsaturated oil.

Ethyl ether extract: Mainly 'bonducin' and a small amount of an oily material.

Chloroform extract: A very small amount of 'bonducin' and a large amount of a semi-solid material of the consistency of rubber.

Ethyl acetate extract: A small amount of a resinous matter.

Alcohol extract: A large amount of sucrose, saponin and a very small amount of glucose.

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Diagrammatic Scheme of Analysis of Alcoholic Extract of Kernels.

III. CHLOROFORM EXTRACT

Bitter principle (A) and a large amount of a substance of the consistency of rubber (G).

IV. ETHYL ACETATE EXTRACT

Very small amount of a waxy residue; nothing definite.

V. ALCOHOL EXTRACT

tested with water

<p><i>Soluble</i> : Precipitated with basic lead acetate.</p>	<p><i>Insoluble</i> : Small amount of a resinous material; nothing definite.</p>
<p><i>Precipitate</i> : Treated with hydrogen sulphide and filtered.</p>	<p><i>Filtrate</i> : De-leaded, concentrated, digested with alcohol and crystallised.</p>
<p><i>Filtrate</i> : Saponin (H).</p>	<p>Sucrose (I)</p> <p><i>Filtrate</i> : Glucosazone (J) (m. p. 305°).</p>